

Multipl Skleroz Hastalarında Zihin-Beden Egzersizlerinin Yorgunluk, Denge ve Yaşam Kalitesi Üzerine Etkisi: Sistematik Derleme ve Meta-Analiz

Effect of Mind Body Exercises on Fatigue, Balance, and Quality of Life in Patients with Multiple Sclerosis: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

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Öz

Amaç: MS hastalarının rehabilitasyonunda giderek yaygınlığı artan yoga ve pilates gibi zihin-beden egzersizleri (ZBE), iskelet kaslarında germe ve gevşeme, fiziksel koordinasyon eğitimi, nefes alma, hareket kontrolü ve dikkatin yönetimini içeren orta düzeyde aerobik egzersizlerdir. Bu çalışma, ZBE'nin MS hastalarında yorgunluk, denge ve sağlıkla ilgili yaşam kalitesi üzerindeki etkilerini araştırmayı amaçlamaktadır.

Yöntem: PubMed, Science Direct, Web of Science ve Ulakbim veritabanları tarandı. Çalışmalardan arama, seçim ve veri çıkarma işlemleri iki bağımsız değerlendirici tarafından gerçekleştirildi. Bu meta-analizde, etki büyüklüklerini Standardize Ortalama Fark (SOF) olarak raporlayan meta analiz için rastgele etkiler modeli kullanıldı.

Sonuçlar: Meta-analiz, toplam 791 katılımcıyla 19 randomize kontrollü klinik çalışmayı içermektedir. MS hastalarında yorgunluk (SOF: 0,14, %95 CI=-0,07, 0,34, I²=0%) ve denge (SOF: 0,51, %95 CI=0,00, 1,02, I²=73%) açısından ZBE ve fiziksel egzersiz arasında istatistiksel olarak anlamlı bir fark tespit edilmedi. ZBE, egzersiz yapmayan gruba göre yorgunluğu (SOF: 0,82, %95 CI = -1,23, -0,41, I²=71%) ve dengeyi (SOF: 1,36, %95 CI = 0,39, 2,32, I²=88%) geliştirmede daha etkili bulundu, ancak fiziksel (SOF: 0,04, %95 CI = -0,42, 0,34, I²=0%) veya mental sağlıkla ilişkili yaşam kalitesi (SOF: 0,04, %95 CI = -0,42, 0,34, I²=0%) için daha etkili değildi.

Tartışma: Bu meta-analiz ile, ZBE'nin MS hastalarında yorgunluk ve dengeyi yönetmek için fiziksel egzersize uygun bir alternatif olarak değerlendirilebileceği sonucuna varıldı. ZBE egzersiz yapmamaya kıyasla daha fazla fayda gösterdi. ZBE'nin sağlıkla ilgili yaşam kalitesi üzerinde ek bir yarar sağlamadığı belirlendi.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Denge; Egzersiz; Yorgunluk; Multipl skleroz; Yaşam kalitesi

Abstract

Purpose: Mind-body exercises (MBEs) such as Yoga and Pilates, which are increasingly used in the rehabilitation of patients with MS (pwMS), are moderate aerobic exercises that include stretching and relaxation in skeletal muscle, physical coordination training, breathing, movement control, and attention regulation. This study aims to investigate the effects of MBEs on fatigue, balance, and health-related quality of life (HRQoL) in pwMS.

Methods: PubMed, Science Direct, Web of Science, and Ulakbim databases were searched. Search, selection, and data extraction from the studies were performed by two independent reviewers. The random effects model for meta-analysis, reporting effect sizes as Standardized Mean Difference (SMD) was used in this meta-analysis.

Results: This meta-analysis included 19 randomized controlled clinical trials with 791 participants in total. No statistically significant difference was detected between MBEs and physical exercise in terms of fatigue (SMD: 0.14, 95% CI=-0.07, 0.34, I²=0%) and balance (SMD: 0.51, 95% CI=0.00, 1.02, I²=73%) in pwMS. MBEs are more effective compared to no exercise for improving fatigue (SMD: 0.82, 95% CI = -1.23, -0.41, I²=71%) and balance (SMD: 1.36, 95% CI = 0.39, 2.32, I²=88%) but not physical (SMD: 0.04, 95% CI = -0.42, 0.34, I²=0%) or mental HRQoL (SMD: 0.04, 95% CI = -0.42, 0.34, I²=0%) in pwMS.

Conclusion: This meta-analysis concluded that MBEs may be considered a feasible alternative to physical exercise for managing fatigue and balance in pwMS. MBEs showed greater benefits compared to no exercise. MBEs did not provide any additional benefit on HRQoL.

Keywords: Balance; Exercise; Fatigue; Multiple sclerosis; Quality of life

1. INTRODUCTION

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is a chronic inflammatory disease characterized by demyelination and axonal loss in the central nervous system (CNS) (1). MS symptoms vary depending on whether part of the CNS is affected. Spasticity, fatigue, loss of muscle strength, tremor, balance problems, exercise intolerance, pain, sensory disorders, bladder and bowel problems, cognitive dysfunctions, depression, and sleep disorders are among the clinical symptoms (2).

Fatigue is one of the most common symptoms found in patients with MS (pwMS), causing disability and having a major impact on daily living activities and health-related quality of life (HRQoL) (3,4). It was shown that more than half of the patients had fatigue symptoms, and the prevalence of fatigue varied between 75% to 90% (5-7). Non-pharmacological approaches for the management of fatigue include energy conservation techniques, fatigue management training, cognitive behavioral therapy, psycho-behavioral interventions such as mindfulness, and mind-body exercises (MBEs) (8).

Balance issues are another highly prevalent symptom in pwMS that can appear even in the early stages of the disease and are seen in more than half of the patients (9). Evaluation and treatment of balance problems from the early period are of great importance (10). Exercise interventions and rehabilitation methods are non-pharmacological options for treating balance disorders in pwMS (11).

Health-related quality of life is negatively affected in pwMS (12,13). The symptoms of the disease, the disease is often diagnosed in young adults, the lack of convincing disease-modifying treatments, and the uncertain nature of the disease are among the factors that lower patients' HRQoL (14). Aerobic exercise and physiotherapy approaches, in particular, are effective in improving HRQoL in pwMS (15).

Mind-body exercises are defined as low-cost, easy-to-apply, moderate-intensity aerobic exercises that include stretching and relaxation in skeletal muscle, physical coordination training, breathing, movement control, and attention regulation (16). Yoga, Qi Gong, Tai Chi, and Pilates are the most popular MBEs (17,18). When compared to traditional aerobic or strengthening exercises, MBEs are lower in intensity and slower in pace. For this reason, it is stated that MBEs are especially suitable for the elderly and those with chronic diseases (19). Due to their adaptable intensity and holistic structure, these exercises

may be particularly suitable for pwMS with varying physical abilities. By targeting both physical and psychosocial domains, MBEs have the potential to support symptom management and improve outcomes such as fatigue, balance, self-efficacy, mental well-being, and quality of life (20).

This study aims to investigate the effects of MBEs on fatigue, balance, and HRQoL in pwMS compared to non-intervention and traditional standardized exercise interventions.

2. METHODS

Protocol and registration

This meta-analysis was performed following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines (21). The selected search strategy and analysis methods were prospectively recorded in the PROSPERO database (registration number: CRD42021259747).

Search strategy

Electronic searches were carried out between 01.01.2000 and 15.05.2021 in the following databases: PubMed, Science Direct, Web of Science, Ulakbim. The following MeSH terms and Boolean operators were used: "Multiple Sclerosis" AND "Tai Chi" or "Pilates" or "Qigong" or "Qi gong" or "mind-body exercise" or "mind-body exercises" AND "Fatigue" or "Balance" or "Postural Control" or "Quality of Life". Studies were selected based on titles and abstracts that met the selection criteria.

Eligibility criteria

Inclusion and exclusion criteria were made according to the PICOS strategy (22): P (Patient) - Individuals with Multiple Sclerosis (MS); I (Intervention) - Treatment with MBEs (Tai Chi, Yoga, Pilates, Qi Gong (17); C (Comparison) - comparison group with or without physical exercises; O (Outcome) - fatigue, balance and quality of life; S (Study design) - randomized controlled clinical trials. Studies in English, German, and Turkish were included. Studies without full text (protocols and conference presentations, congress booklet, papers), animal studies, pilot studies, and case reports were excluded.

Study selection

The titles, keywords, and abstracts determined through the

databases were searched independently by two researchers. The studies identified in the search results were transferred from databases into EndNote X9. Duplications were later removed. First, the titles and abstracts of the identified studies were reviewed by the authors for convenience. After the initial screening, relevant studies were selected according to the inclusion criteria, and studies that did not meet the inclusion criteria were excluded by cross-checking. A final list of eligible studies was compiled, and any disagreement was resolved by contacting a third researcher. After this stage, full-text copies of all identified articles were reviewed, and their compliance with the inclusion and exclusion criteria was re-evaluated. In addition, reference lists of relevant articles were reviewed by manual searches. Articles that did not meet the selection criteria were not included.

Data extraction

From each selected study, general information on the title, first author, publication year, country, number of cases and controls included, description of cases and controls, assessment methods, and characteristics of interventions were extracted and tabulated for qualitative synthesis (Table 1).

Health-related quality of life was examined in two subgroups as physical and mental HRQoL. Since MBEs may also provide additional benefits for mental well-being, studies that reported HRQoL separately as physical HRQoL and mental HRQoL were included, whereas those that reported a single overall HRQoL score were excluded. If physical composite score (PCS) or mental composite score (MCS) on the Short Form-36 (SF-36) scale were reported, they were directly included in the analysis; otherwise, among the subgroup scores, the physical health subgroup scores for physical HRQoL and the mental health subgroup scores for mental HRQoL were included.

Quality appraisal

The risk of bias was assessed using the Cochrane Collaboration Risk of Bias Tools in Review Manager software version 5.4 and classified as low, unclear, and high risk (23). Bias risk was evaluated independently by two authors. The bias risk assessment is based on seven domains, including random sequence generation, concealment of allocation, blinding of participants, blinding outcome assessment, missing outcome data, selective reporting, and other sources of bias.

Synthesis methods

Meta-analysis of the included studies was conducted using RevMan 5.3 (The Nordic Cochrane Centre, Copenhagen, Denmark). Forest plots were created in order to provide a pictorial overview of the study results. Standardized mean differences with 95% confidence intervals were used for analyzing continuous variables. A random-effects model was used for pooling the data. Heterogeneity was assessed using the I^2 statistic, and I^2 values of 25%, 50%, and 75% was considered as small, moderate, and high degrees of heterogeneity, respectively.

3. RESULTS

Study selection

A total of 293 records were obtained from the database search. After excluding 167 duplicate records, the remaining 126 records were screened for title and abstract. When the abstract and title of the studies were examined, 66 studies were excluded. The full texts of the remaining 60 articles were reviewed, and 19 studies that met our eligibility criteria were included in the quantitative synthesis. The flowchart of the research selection process is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the study

Study characteristics

This meta-analysis comprised 19 studies in total. All studies were randomized controlled trials (24-42). Six studies took place in Iran (30,25,26,40,35,36), three in Ireland (31,32,34), three in The United States of America (39,27,42), two in Turkey (38,24), and one in each of these countries: Slovenia (41), Israel (37), United Kingdom (33), Brazil (28), and Canada (29). Included studies compared MBEs to either physical exercise or no exercise. Nine studies compared MBEs to no exercise (26-32,35,40), five studies compared MBEs to physical exercise (24,33,37,38,41), and five studies compared MBEs to both no exercise and physical exercise (25,34,36,39,42). The intervention groups in the studies were as follows: Pilates in nine studies (24,29-33,35,37,38), yoga in nine studies (25,26,28,34,36,39-42), and Qigong in one study (27). The number of MBEs therapy sessions ranged from 10 to 36. The duration of the MBEs programs ranged from eight weeks to six months, and sessions lasted 30–90 minutes, which were performed one to three days per week. Power analysis was reported in seven (24,29,32-35,39) of the 19 studies included in our study. In 10 of these studies (25-27,30,36-38,40-42), no information was provided on whether power analysis was conducted. It was stated that power analysis was not performed in two studies (28,31). The main characteristics of the 19 eligible studies are summarized in Table 1.

Participant characteristics

The studies in this analysis included a total of 791 participants. The sample size in the studies varied from 12 to 175 participants. The overall number of participants in MBEs were 351. The number of participants in MBEs groups ranged from 5 to 63. The participants' average age ranges from 30 to 54. The degree of disability was reported in all the studies. Expanded Disability Status Scale (EDSS) in 12 studies (24-26,39,36,33,37,28,40,38,41,30), Patient Determined Disease Steps (PDDS) in four studies (32,29,42,31), Mobility subscale of the Guys Neurological Disability Rating Scale in one study (34), Disability score index (DSI) in one study (35), and ability to walk 50 feet without assistance in one study (27). In studies that reported MS patients' EDSS and PDDS scores, the patients had a score of six or less. The DSI scores of the patients ranged from 3-5 and the Mobility subscale of the Guys Neurological Disability Rating scale score of 0, 1, or 2 on the scale were included.

Outcome characteristics

13 studies measured the impact of MBEs on fatigue (25-27,30-32,34,37-42), 12 on balance (24-29,33,35-38,42), and four on HRQoL (26,27,29,39). Fatigue was assessed with Modified Fatigue Impact Scale (MFIS) in eight studies (27,30-32,34,37,38,41), Fatigue Severity Scale (FSS) in three studies (25,26,40), PROMIS Fatigue-Short Form 8a (adult v1.0) in one study (42), and Multi-Dimensional Fatigue Inventory (MFI) in one study (39). Balance was assessed with Functional Reach Test (FRT) in two studies (35,37), Timed up and Go (TUG) in four studies (27,35,37,42), Berg Balance Scale (BBS) in six studies (25,26,28,35,37,38), Biodex in two studies (24,36), Activities-Specific Balance Confidence (ABC) in two studies (24,33), and Fullerton Advanced Balance Scale (FABS) in one study (29). When a study included more than one measure for balance, the outcome included in the meta-analysis was chosen according to the following order of priority: Biodex (Limits of Stability, then postural stability), BBS, TUG, ABC, FABS. The ranking we made for the selection of balance measurements was based on the study by Allen et al. (43), the degree of objectivity of the particular measurements, and their frequency of use. HRQoL was assessed with MSQoL-54 in two studies (26,29), SF-36 in one study (39), and PROMIS in one study (27).

Risk of bias in studies and heterogeneity

The assessments of methodological quality were displayed in Figure 2 and Figure 3. 13 studies (68.4%) reported adequate methods for random sequence generation and 11 studies (57.9%) reported adequate methods for allocation concealment. A high risk of blinding to participants and personnel was observed in all the studies. Eight studies (42.1%) reported adequate methods for blinding of outcome assessment and 16 studies (84.2%) for attrition bias. Low risk of reporting bias was observed in all the studies. Low risk of other risk of bias was observed in 13 studies (68.4%) (Figure 2, Figure 3).

Figure 2. Risk of bias graph: Review authors' judgements about each methodological quality item presented as percentages across all included studies

	Random sequence generation (selection bias)	Allocation concealment (selection bias)	Blinding of participants and personnel (performance bias)	Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Other bias
Abasiyanik 2020	+	?	+	+	+	+	+
Ahmadi 2010	?	?	+	+	+	+	+
Ahmadi 2013	?	?	+	+	+	+	+
Buttolph 2021	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
de Oliveira 2016	+	?	+	+	+	+	+
Duff 2018	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Eftekhari 2018	+	+	+	+	+	+	?
Fleming 2019	+	+	+	?	+	+	?
Fleming 2021	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Fox 2016	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Garrett 2012	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Gheitasi 2021	+	+	+	?	+	+	?
Hosseini 2018	?	?	+	?	+	+	+
Kalron 2016	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Kucuk 2016	+	+	+	+	?	+	?
Oken 2004	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Razzazian 2016	+	+	+	+	+	+	?
Velikonja 2010	?	?	+	?	+	+	+
Young 2019	+	+	+	+	+	+	?

Figure 3. Risk of bias summary: Review authors' judgements about each methodological quality item for each included study

Adverse events

It was reported that no adverse events occurred in seven (29,31-33,35,37,39) of the 19 studies. There was no information provided on whether there were adverse events in nine of the studies (25,26,28,30,34,36,38,40,41), and in one study (24), adverse events were questioned, but the outcome was not reported. Adverse events were documented in two studies (27,42). In one of them (42), the reported adverse event was a stroke, which was not related with the intervention; in another study (27), three adverse events potentially related to the intervention were reported: lower back pain, increased leg spasticity, and mild back pain.

Meta-analysis

Mind Body Exercises versus Physical Exercises – Outcome: Fatigue

Seven studies investigated the effect of MBEs and physical exercise on fatigue (25,34,37-39,41,42). Based on the random-effects model, there was no significant difference between the effect of MBEs and physical exercise on fatigue, with a Standardized Mean Difference (SMD) of 0.14 (95% CI=-0.07, 0.34; p=0.19) having a small heterogeneity (I²=0%) (Figure 4).

Mind Body Exercises versus Physical Exercises – Outcome: Balance

Seven studies investigated the effect of MBEs and physical exercise on balance (24,25,33,36-38,42). Based on the random-effects model, there was no significant difference between the effect of MBEs and physical exercise on balance, with a SMD of 0.51 (95% CI=0.00, 1.02; p=0.05), having a moderate heterogeneity (I²=73%) (Figure 4).

Mind Body Exercises versus Physical Exercises – Outcome: Quality of life, Physical Health

One study investigated the effect of MBEs and physical exercise on HRQoL (39). For this reason, a meta-analysis could not be conducted; however, there was no significant difference between the effect of MBEs and physical exercise on HRQoL: physical health, with a SMD of 0.03 (95% CI=-0.62, 0.69; p=0.92) (Figure 4).

Mind Body Exercises versus Physical Exercises – Outcome: Quality of life, Mental Health

One study investigated the effect of MBEs and physical exercise on HRQoL (39). For this reason, a meta-analysis could not be conducted; however, there was a significant difference between the effect of MBEs and physical exercise on HRQoL: mental health in favour of physical exercise, with a SMD of -0.77 (95% CI=-1.45, -0.09; p=0.03) (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Forest plot of the effect of MBEs and physical exercise on fatigue, balance and quality of life; physical health, quality of life; mental health

Mind Body Exercises versus No Exercise – Outcome: Fatigue

Ten studies investigated the effect of MBEs on fatigue (25-27,30-32,34,39,40,42). Based on the random-effects model, there was a significant difference between the effect of MBEs and no exercise on fatigue in favor of MBEs, with a SMD of -0.82 (95% CI = -1.23, -0.41; p < 0.0001), having a moderate heterogeneity (I²=71%). Negative SMD values support improvement in fatigue outcomes (Figure 5).

Mind Body Exercises versus No Exercise – Outcome: Balance

Eight studies investigated the effect of MBEs on balance (25-29,35,36,42). Based on the random-effects model, there was a significant difference between the effect of MBEs and no exercise on balance in favor of MBEs, with a SMD of 1.36 (95% CI = 0.39, 2.32; p = 0.006), having a high heterogeneity (I²=88%). Positive SMD values support improvement in balance outcomes (Figure 5).

Mind Body Exercises versus No Exercise – Outcome: Quality of life, Physical Health

Four studies investigated the effect of MBEs on HRQoL (26,27,29,39). Based on the random-effects model, there was no significant difference between the effect of MBEs and no exercise on HRQoL: physical health, with a SMD

of -0.04 (95% CI = -0.42, 0.34; p = 0.83), having a small heterogeneity (I²=0%) (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Forest plot of the effect of MBEs and no exercise on fatigue, balance, and quality of life; physical health, quality of life; mental health

Mind Body Exercises versus No Exercise – Outcome: Quality of life, Mental Health

Four studies investigated the effect of MBEs on HRQoL (26,27,29,39). Based on the random-effects model, there was no significant difference between the effect of MBEs and no exercise on HRQoL: mental health, with a SMD of -0.04 (95% CI = -0.42, 0.34; p = 0.82), having a small heterogeneity (I²=0%) (Figure 5).

4. DISCUSSION

In this study, the existing scientific evidence was analyzed to establish the efficacy of MBEs in the rehabilitation of pwMS. It was provided by comparing the effectiveness of MBEs to no exercise and physical exercise. Since randomized controlled trials provide more reliable evidence compared to other study designs, we only included them in our analysis. Therefore, the findings of this study would be presented more accurately. This systematic review and meta-analysis included 19 randomized controlled trials evaluating the effectiveness of MBEs on fatigue, balance, and HRQoL in pwMS.

According to the findings of the meta-analysis, MBEs had similar effects on fatigue and balance as physical exercise. Both types of exercise have been shown to reduce fatigue and enhance balance in pwMS. In addition, it was found that MBEs are more effective compared to no exercise for improving fatigue and balance, but not HRQoL. Based on this meta-analysis, we have concluded that MBEs may be a feasible alternative to physical exercises for improving fatigue and balance in pwMS.

At all stages of the disease, fatigue is one of the most devastating symptoms experienced by more than half of pwMS [7]. In the management of fatigue in pwMS, a range of intervention approaches, including exercise interventions, behavioral interventions, educational strategies, and medication, should be considered [44]. The

results of this study demonstrate that MBEs do not appear to differ substantially from physical exercise with respect to fatigue management. In a meta-analysis examining the effectiveness of exercise modalities and behavioral interventions on fatigue in pwMS, it was reported that balance exercise and cognitive behavioral therapy appear to be the most promising interventions for fatigue [45]. In addition, it was also reported that physical exercise interventions such as aerobic, resistance, flexibility, and combined programs were effective for fatigue management in the short-term. However, that meta-analysis did not include MBEs [45]. In this meta-analysis, which showed that MBEs are as effective as physical exercises in the management of fatigue, interventions in

Table 1 General characteristics of the studies

Authors (Year)	Country	Sample	Study frequency	Comparative group	Interventions	Outcome measure	Main results
Abasiyanik et al. (2020)	Turkey	33 participants MBE: 16 PE: 17	MBE: 24 sessions 8 weeks 3 times/week. 55-60 min. PE: 24 sessions 8 weeks 3 times/week.	PE: Standardized home exercise reflected routine clinical practice and aimed to improve spinal column, upper and lower extremity flexibility, strength, trunk, and pelvic stability, and balance.	MBE: Pilates. Each session started with a warm-up and ended with a cool-down. One session group exercise a week plus a two-day home exercise program.	Balance: The Biodex Balance System, FES-I, ABC	There were statistically significant differences in limits of stability (p=0.038), overall postural stability (p=0.028), and mediolateral postural stability scores (p=0.017) between the groups. Anteroposterior postural stability (p=0.177), FES-I (0.385) and ABC scores (p=0.114) were not significantly different between the groups.
Ahmadi et al. (2010)	Iran	21 participants MBE: 11 NE: 10	MBE: 24 sessions 8 weeks 3 times /week 60-70 min.	NE: No exercise during the study period	MBE: Hatha yoga. The postures started with stretching techniques followed by standing, supine and prone-lying and sitting postures	Fatigue: FSS Balance: BBS HRQoL: MSQoL-54	There were significant differences in FSS scores (p=0.01), BBS scores (p<0.001) and physical health composite (p=0.04) and mental health composite (p=0.01) scores of MSQOL-54 between the groups.

Table 1 (Continued)

Authors (Year)	Country	Sample	Study frequency	Comparative group	Interventions	Outcome measure	Main results
Ahmadi et al. (2013)	Iran	31 participants MBE: 11 PE: 10 NE: 10	MBE: 24 sessions 8 weeks 3 times/week 60-70 min. PE: 24 sessions 8 weeks 3 times/week 50 min.	PE: Treadmill training. Training intensity was 40-75% age-predicted maximal heart rate. NE: No exercise during the study period	MBE: Hatha yoga. Hatha yoga has three basic components, postures (asanas), breathing techniques (pranayama) and meditation (dhyana).	Fatigue: FSS Balance: BBS	There were no statistically significant differences between treadmill training group and yoga group regarding balance (p = 0.76) and fatigue scores (p = 0.99). There were statistically significant differences between yoga group and control group regarding balance (p = 0.001) and fatigue scores (p = 0.03).
Buttolph et al. (2021)	United States of America	16 participants MBE: 6 NE: 10	MBE: 10 sessions 10 weeks 1 time/week 60-90 min.	NE: No exercise during the study period	MBE: Qigong The qigong styles available to participants, which include different movements and other components, were dayan (wild goose) qigong, jin jing gong (tendon and channel) qigong, huo long jing (fire dragon meridian) qigong, wu xing (5 elements) qigong.	Fatigue: MFIS Balance: TUG HRQoL: PROMIS	There were little differences in HRQoL measures between groups. MFIS suggested reduced fatigue following the qigong intervention. There was no significant differences in TUG scores between groups.

Table 1 (Continued)

Authors (Year)	Country	Sample	Study frequency	Comparative group	Interventions	Outcome measure	Main results
de Oliveira et al. (2016)	Brazil	12 participants MBE:6 NE:6	MBE: 28 sessions 6 months 1 time/week 60 min.	NE: Waitlist control	MBE: Yoga. Following steps: stretching postures (asanas); breathing control techniques (pranayama); meditation techniques (dhyana) and relaxation techniques (nidra).	Balance: BBS	There was a significant difference in BBS scores between groups (p=0.013). The BBS score was higher in the MBE group than in the control group.
Duff et al. (2018)	Canada	30 participants MBE: 15 NE: 15	MBE: 24 sessions 12 weeks 2 times/week 50 min.	NE: Participants received only the once-weekly 1-hour massage therapy session.	MBE: Pilates Each session started with a warm-up and ended with a cool-down. Also received a weekly 1-hour massage	Balance: FABS HRQoL: MSQOL-54	Balance (p=0.16) and physical (p=0.60) or mental (p=0.71) quality of life scores were not significantly different between the groups.
Eftekhari et al. (2018)	Iran	25 participants MBE: 13 NE: 12	MBE: 24 sessions 8 weeks 3 times/week	NE: No exercise during the study period	MBE: Pilates The mat Pilates training consisted of special exercises which were based on core stability.	Fatigue: MFIS	There were significant differences in MFIS scores (p<0.001) between the groups.

Table 1 (Continued)

Authors (Year)	Country	Sample	Study frequency	Comparative group	Interventions	Outcome measure	Main results
Fleming et al. (2019)	Ireland	12 participants MBE: 5 NE: 7	MBE: 16 sessions 8 weeks 2 times / week 60 min.	NE: No exercise during the study period	MBE: Pilates. Pilates sessions were comprised of mat-based beginner's level exercises. There were two Pilates exercise groups; a supervised Pilates and a home-based Pilates group.	Fatigue: MFIS	Compared to the no exercise group, scores for the home-based exercise group were significantly lower for total fatigue ($p \leq 0.02$).
Fleming et al. (2021)	Ireland	80 participants MBE: 39 NE: 41	MBE: 16 sessions 8 weeks 2 times/week 60 min.	NE: No exercise during the study period	MBE: Pilates. Home-based Pilates exercises supported by a DVD.	Fatigue: MFIS	There were statistically significant differences in total MFIS scores between groups ($p < 0.05$).
Fox et al. (2016)	United Kingdom	68 participants MBE: 33 PE: 35	MBE: 12 sessions 12 weeks 1 time/week 30 min. PE: 12 sessions 12 weeks 1 time/week 30 min.	PE: Standardized exercise	MBE: Pilates. Exercises that placed upon voluntary activation of the deep abdominal muscles and progressed at each session according to the individual's abilities. And individualized 15-minute daily home exercise program.	Balance: ABC	ABC score was not significantly different between the groups.

Table 1. (Continued)

Authors (Year)	Country	Sample	Study frequency	Comparative group	Interventions	Outcome measure	Main results
Garrett et al. (2012)	Ireland	175 participants MBE: 63 PE: 63 NE: 49	MBE: 10 sessions 10 weeks 1 time/week. PE: 10 sessions 10 weeks 1 time/week. Plus, aerobic session 2 times/week (from week 6) 30 min.	PE: Resistance exercises that bodyweight or free weights. In addition, were advised to aerobic exercise. NE: No exercise during the study period	MBE: Yoga. The intervention is also not predefined, but generally focused on breathing exercises, relaxation, or body centering.	Fatigue: MFIS	MFIS total and MFIS physical scores were higher in MBE and PE than the control group. For all groups, there was no significant difference in MFIS cognitive score compared to the control group.
Gheitasi et al. (2021)	Iran	30 participants MBE: 15 NE: 15	MBE: 36 sessions 12 weeks 3 times/week. 60 min.	NE: only receive usual care by their medical doctor.	MBE: Pilates. 10 min. warm-up exercises following 40-45 min Pilates exercise and 5 min of cool-down.	Balance: BBS, TUG, FRT	BBS, TUG and FRT scores were higher in the MBE group compared with the control group after training for 12 weeks. In addition, a significant difference was observed between the groups in terms of the mean of functional balance indices in the post-test results.

Table 1 (Continued)

Authors (Year)	Country	Sample	Study frequency	Comparative group	Interventions	Outcome measure	Main results
Hosseini et al. (2018)	Iran	26 participants MBE: 9 PE: 9 NE: 8	MBE: 24 sessions 8 weeks 3 times/week 60-70 min. PE: 24 sessions 8 weeks 3 time/week 40-50 min.	PE: Home-based resistant training. 5-10 min. warm-up exercises following 25-30 min Pilates exercise and 10 min of cool-down. NE: routine physical activity	MBE: Hatha Yoga. Includes exercises in different positions. Each pose lasted for approximately 10-30 seconds.	Balance: Computerized Biodex.	There was a near significant difference in open-eye balance changes between groups. There was no significant difference in closed-eye balance, single-leg and open-eye balance tests between groups.
Kalron et al. (2016)	Israel	45 participants MBE: 22 PE: 23	MBE: 12 sessions 12 weeks 1 time/week 30 min. PE: 12 sessions 12 weeks 1 time/week	PE: A standardized program of physiotherapy exercises aimed at improving trunk and pelvic stability, lower limb muscle length, strength, balance and control of movement was used according to the Bobath concept.	MBE: Pilates. The core stability exercises were selected. The exercises were designed to challenge progressively trunk control by gradually increasing the limb load and/or by reducing the base of support.	Fatigue: MFIS Balance: FRT, TUG, BBS, FSST	There was no significant differences in MFIS scores between groups (P=0.683). There were statistically significant differences in FRT (p=0.003), TUG (p=0.023) and FSST (0.031) scores between groups. There was no statistically significant difference in BBS scores between groups (p=0.215).

Table 1 (Continued)

Authors (Year)	Country	Sample	Study frequency	Comparative group	Interventions	Outcome measure	Main results
Kucuk et al. (2016)	Turkey	20 participants MBE: 11 PE: 9	MBE: 16 sessions 8 weeks 2 times/week. 45-60 min. PE: 16 sessions 8 weeks 2 times/week	PE: Traditional exercises including strength, balance, and coordination exercises	MBE: Pilates. Each session was comprised of a 10 min warm-up, 25-45 min of mat exercises, and 10 min cool-down.	Fatigue: MFIS Balance: BBS	There were no statistically significant differences in BBS and MFIS between groups.
Oken et al. (2004)	United States of America	57 participants MBE: 22 NE: 20 PE: 15	MBE: 26 sessions 26 weeks 1 time/week 90 min. PE: 26 sessions 26 weeks 1 time/week Bicycling was continued until MS symptom onset or personal goal achievement.	PE: The aerobic exercise consisted of bicycling on recumbent or dual action stationary bicycles. Cycling is a regular exercise mode, but also a periodical exercise option with a Swiss ball was given. NE: No exercise during the study period	MBE: Iyengar yoga. 19 poses were given, with each pose supported.	Fatigue: MFI HRQoL: SF-36	There were significant differences only in general fatigue domains of the MFI with either intervention (p<0.01). There were significant differences in energy and fatigue subscore of SF-36 with either intervention (p<0.01). The Health Transitions subscore on the SF-36 was different in the yoga group (p<0.01).

Table 1 (Continued)

Authors (Year)	Country	Sample	Study frequency	Comparative group	Interventions	Outcome measure	Main results
Razzazian et al. (2016)	Iran	36 participants MBE: 18 NE: 18	MBE: 24 sessions 8 weeks 3 times/week. 60 min.	NE: Participants in the nonexercise condition met two to three times a week in the hospital for about 60 to 90 min.	MBE: Hatha Yoga. A typical session consisted of centering: breathing exercises, meditation; sun salute; different and increasingly demanding standing postures; supported head and shoulder stands; different twists and bends; corpse pose at the end of the session.	Fatigue: FSS	There was significant difference in FSS score changes between groups. The fatigue decreased over time in the MBE but not in the NE.
Velikonja et al. (2010)	Slovenia	20 participants MBE: 10 PE:10	MBE: 10 sessions 10 weeks 1 time /week PE: 10 sessions 10 weeks 1 time /week	PE: Sports climbing	MBE: Hatha yoga.	Fatigue: MFIS	There was a significant effect of Sports climbing on the level of fatigue (p= 0.015). There were no significant differences in fatigue in the yoga program.

Table 1 (Continued)

Authors (Year)	Country	Sample	Study frequency	Comparative group	Interventions	Outcome measure	Main results
Young et al. (2019)	United States of America	54 participants MBE:26 NE: 28	MBE: 36 sessions 12 weeks 3 times/week. 60 min, PE: 36 sessions 12 weeks 3 times/week. 60 min,	PE: aimed to progressively improve mobility using combinations of movement forms that were structured to target 3 fitness components: strength, cardiorespiratory endurance, and balance. NE: Waitlist control	MBE: Iyengar approach to Hatha yoga. Based on the 3-Mountain format, which included a warm-up phase (Mountain 1), work phase (Mountain 2), and cool-down phase (Mountain 3). Each class ended with relaxation.	Fatigue: PROMIS Fatigue-Short Form 8a (adult v1.0) Balance: TUG	There were no statistically significant differences in balance and fatigue between groups

MBE: mind-body exercise, PE: physical exercise, NE: no exercise, HRQoL: health-related quality of life, MFIS: modified fatigue impact scale, FRT: functional reach test, TUG: timed up and go, BBS: berg balance scale, FSST: four square step, FSS: fatigue severity scale, MSQOL-54: multiple sclerosis quality of life-54, MFI: multi-dimensional fatigue inventory, SF-36: short form-36, PROMIS: the patient-reported outcomes measurement information system, ABC: the activities specific balance confidence, FES-I: the falls efficacy scale, FABS: fullerton advanced balance scale, MusiQoL: multiple sclerosis international quality of life questionnaire.

the physical exercise control groups included aerobic exercise, strength, balance, and coordination exercises, or combined exercises. Another network meta-analysis investigated the effects of different exercise interventions on fatigue management in pwMS [46]. The exercise interventions included in the selected studies in this meta-analysis were aerobic, resistance, aerobic with resistance, balance, combined exercise, body weight support, and

MBEs (yoga or Pilates) [46]. According to the results of the previous network meta-analysis, combined interventions are the most effective exercise approach for managing fatigue in pwMS [46]. Unlike other meta-analyses, only studies with physical exercise intervention and/or no exercise in the control group were included in this study. Therefore, it was aimed to reveal the isolated effects of MBEs against both no exercise and physical

exercise. In our study, we determined that MBEs were effective in the management of fatigue compared to no exercise. In addition, MBEs proved to be as effective as physical exercise for fatigue management. Therefore, we believe that MBEs may be an alternative intervention to physical exercise for managing fatigue in pwMS.

Balance disorders are another common symptom in pwMS [9]. In the treatment of balance problems, there are non-pharmacological treatment options available, including exercise interventions and technology-based interventions [11]. Dual-task training [47], virtual reality, exergames [48], and aerobic training [49] were also revealed as beneficial interventions for MS patients' balance disorders in the literature. In the study by Bymes et al. [11], which examined the effects of non-pharmacological approaches on symptoms in pwMS, two studies included MBEs. Bymes et al. [11] reported that alternative interventions such as reflexology, yoga, and Pilates had a moderate effect on improving balance. One of our study's strengths is that it focuses only on the effectiveness of MBEs in pwMS. A previous meta-analysis examining the effects of Pilates exercises in pwMS determined that Pilates was effective in improving balance [50]. In this meta analysis, it was determined that MBEs were more effective than no exercise in improving balance disorders; however, this finding should be interpreted with caution due to the high level of heterogeneity observed across the included studies. The substantial heterogeneity observed in the balance outcomes may reflect methodological and clinical diversity among the included studies, including variations in the type of MBEs interventions, balance measurement instruments, and differences in intervention duration, intensity, and frequency. Pilates, yoga, and Qigong exercises consist of exercises that involve continuous movement of the body's center of gravity. Therefore, they may improve patients' balance control by strengthening the extremities and improving proprioception [41]. Considering MBEs also provide similar benefits as physical exercise, they may be an alternative to physical exercise for improving balance as well.

Health-related quality of life measures the satisfaction of individuals with their physical, mental, and social well-being. As a result of various symptoms, pwMS experience a significant decrease in their HRQoL [51]. Our meta-analysis included four studies examining the effect of MBEs on HRQoL: two on yoga, one on Qi-gong, and one on Pilates. Also, MSQOL-54 was used in two studies, SF-36 in one study, and PROMIS in one study to evaluate HRQoL. Aerobic exercise and physiotherapy programs are effective interventions for improving HRQoL in pwMS [15]. Accordingly, it may be hypothesized that MBEs, as well, would provide significant benefits on HRQoL. However, in our study, we did not detect such

improvement with MBEs. The literature provides conflicting evidence regarding this topic. Similar to our findings, two meta-analyses reported that yoga interventions did not significantly improve the HRQoL of pwMS [15,52]. On the other hand, another meta-analysis concluded that MBEs improve HRQoL in pwMS [53]. There are plenty of questionnaires available for measuring HRQoL, therefore the heterogeneity of the HRQoL measures used in the studies may hinder providing consistent results on the effects of MBEs on HRQoL. Furthermore, conceptual and methodological differences among HRQoL instruments, including variations in assessed domains, sensitivity to change, and the use of MS-specific versus generic measures, may have contributed to the inconsistent findings across studies. Future research employing standardized and disease-specific HRQoL tools may enhance comparability and clarify the effects of MBEs on HRQoL. In addition, a meta-analysis could not be conducted because only one study examined the effects of physical exercise and MBEs on HRQoL. Considering our study and the conflicting findings in the literature, it may not be appropriate to recommend MBEs as a therapeutic approach to specifically improve HRQoL in these patients. Further studies are required to reach a definitive conclusion on the effects of MBEs on HRQoL in pwMS.

In 63% of the studies included in this meta-analysis, it was not reported whether a priori sample size calculations were conducted, which affects the accuracy of the results as it increases the probability of type II error. On the other hand, neurological impairment levels of pwMS were reported in all studies. EDSS or PDDS scores were the most frequently used measures for reporting neurological impairment level in the studies. The EDSS and PDDS scores of the patients were six or less. As a result, it may not be appropriate to generalize the findings to those with more severe diseases. Another important challenge in translating these findings into clinical practice is the lack of consensus regarding the optimal duration, frequency, and intensity of MBEs, as these parameters varied considerably across the included studies. This heterogeneity limits the ability to provide clear, evidence-based clinical recommendations.

Mind Body Exercises, which are becoming increasingly popular in the general population, provide an entertaining alternative to conventional exercise approaches; therefore, they may be of interest to patients as well. In addition, such exercises require a higher level of mental concentration, which may also provide additional benefits for mental health. Our results suggest that MS patients would also benefit from these features of MBEs.

Study Limitations

Determining the proper dosage is a crucial factor affecting the effectiveness of the interventions. However, we were

unable to determine the optimal treatment dosage in this study. MBEs programs ranged in duration from 8 weeks to 6 months, were used with frequency ranging from 1 to 3 days per week, and there were differences in the duration of the treatment sessions. Consequently, there was a great heterogeneity in the treatment dosages. Further studies are required to determine the optimal dosage. In addition, the MS type of patients included in the study were not homogeneous or it was not reported in some studies, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to the general MS population. Most included studies reported neurological disability levels of EDSS ≤ 6 ; therefore, the findings can be generalized to individuals with mild to moderate MS, but not to those with more severe disability (EDSS >6.5). Furthermore, in nine of the 19 included studies, adverse events were not reported, leading to uncertainty regarding the safety profile of MBEs. Future studies should systematically report safety outcomes to enable a more comprehensive evaluation of potential adverse effects. Due to the nature of exercise training studies, it is often not possible to achieve patient blindness, which may affect the reliability of the results. In addition, the fact that power analysis was documented in only 7 of the studies included in the meta-analysis, while it was either not conducted or not reported in the remaining 12 studies, is a factor that may influence the strength of the meta-analysis results. Lastly, there are plenty of studies in Chinese language investigating the effects of MBEs; however, we were only able to include studies in English, German, and Turkish.

CONCLUSION

This meta-analysis concluded that MBEs have similar benefits as physical exercises on fatigue and balance in pwMS and are more effective than no exercise. However, they failed to improve HRQoL significantly. Based on the current evidence, MBEs such as Pilates and yoga may be recommended as adjunctive or alternative interventions for managing fatigue and balance impairments in pwMS, particularly when tailored to patient preferences, accessibility, and clinical status. Additionally, the effects of MBEs on pwMS have recently gained popularity, and high-quality studies in this area are needed.

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